

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF TECHNOLOGIES FOR ENVIRONMENTAL AND MORAL EDUCATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS BY PROTECTING THE ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *This article describes the role and importance of the technologies of environmental moral education of elementary school students by protecting the environment. There is also information about instilling love for mother nature in elementary school pupils and forming environmental education. How to carry out several methods related to environmental protection and their educational significance were also discussed. The aspects of teaching elementary school pupil's environmental education by protecting the environment were explained.*

Keywords: *primary, class, student, ecology, morality, education, teacher, parents, nature, consciousness, technology, importance, environment, future, resources, water, air.*

In the introduction to the topic, the responsibility and mission of every citizen today is to use natural resources economically and transmit them to the next generation, keeping the environment clean and tidy during today's globalization process. As a result of the development of technology and technology, Our Mother Earth is deliberately in danger, causing the loss of many nature's blessings and their depletion. In search of a solution to this, international organizations and government organizations set a goal and are doing their job. At the same time, the state committee for the protection of the Ecological Party, Ecology and environment Muhit was established in Uzbekistan. "Implementation of a unified state policy in the field of Ecology, Environmental Protection, rational use of Natural Resources, their restoration and Prevention of the negative impact of human activity on nature. In addition to him, our dear President. M. We can see as an example the work carried out under the project "green space" under the leadership of Mirziyoyev. Within the framework of the project, it is planned to plant 200 million bushes of trees. What is the purpose of this? We know that trees produce oxygen. The more trees there are, the more nature will be clean and clear. Everyone should understand this. Here is such a set of tasks. Not only is this organization responsible for the environment, but every person is responsible. Only if all people living in society work on the basis of cooperation in this regard, we will leave a healthy environment for the next generation. Good results can be achieved only if these works are properly brought up in the minds of young people from the family, kindergarten, and starting from primary school. This issue is a topical issue on the world. The correct use of nature is the inexhaustible care that each person has for the next generation.

In the theoretical part of the article, it can be said with special emphasis that today the whole world is puzzling over the preservation of Ecology and bringing it to the coming generation. The most effective and good solution for preserving the environment is the need to formulate environmental education in every person. When we can form in the psyche of a child love and affection for nature from the family, the system of preschool education and primary education, then even during the life of laughter, the child lives as friends with nature. Especially now elementary education, which we will analyze, plays a very important role. The child will be

beginning to fully realize the world at this age. In them, when we can form environmental education, it will be our first good that we do to the environment. As noted above, environmental education should be formed in a child as a general upbringing. It will have helped us closely in this regard if we educate primary school students in the spirit of love for the environment using the works of Oriental thinkers, ancient traditions and traditions correctly. Their works and instructive statements about nature teach the child to increase his knowledge about the environment and use it wisely. Nature, Animal, Man are considered elements of complementary existence. They complement each other. If we take only plants in nature, absorbing their healing, that they are nutrients to primary school students, then the knowledge they receive will remain with them for a lifetime, like a pattern carved into a stone. As evidence, we can cite the following information. For example Abu Ali ibn Sina's " Book II is devoted to medicine, which describes the name of 811 simple medicines of plant, ore and animal origin in alphabetical order and shows which disease each medicine is a cure for. If we give the above information to elementary school students in the lessons of "Natural Science" that plants, animals are very useful to humans, that it is possible to be good through them if a person gets sick, then their love for the green world and animals increases. Simply begin to pour water into the room flowers in his house and wipe their dust. It is necessary that we teach them this consciously.

In the main part of the topic, the creation of ecological and moral education by preserving the environment is facilitated by the fact that elementary school students make things from waste products learned in technology lessons, reducing objects that are released into nature as waste by man. This is the primary environmental preservation and environmental education for them. We need to tell them how great the harm of waste products to the environment is, how much it can make people sick, cause the disappearance of animals. A clean and tidy environment and a clean place also play an important role for people to live healthy. "Of the factors important for the functioning of the human organism, Ibn Sina emphasizes that the geographical and meteorological characteristics of the place of residence, the purity and purity of the air, the importance of water used in the farm are great. The scientist attributes various physiological states of a person's organism to changes in the weather. Relying on the information given above, attention was paid to the cleanliness of the place of residence and emphasis was placed on the suitability of its water for consumption. We know how important water is in nature for human life. We cannot imagine our life without water. In our people, it is not for nothing that the saying "Do not pour water" is said again and again. In Uzbek families, such concepts as "dirty-honest", "Oval", "sin-reward" are used when a more ecological situation occurs (for example, bread falls under the feet, water pollution, cruel treatment of animals, breaking down Martingale-trees, etc.). When children do not yet fully understand the essence of these words, they are given the formation of buds of national environmental behavior. We are encouraged by our people to preserve nature and live with an ecological culture before the children themselves have yet to form their minds.

In the process of teaching primary school students to love the environment, it is environmental education in schools that makes them more interested in organizing events, engaging in them through more practical activities. Alternatively, elementary school students begin to form environmental education in themselves. For example, in elementary school students, one event is organized every month, so that one event involves room flower care. In another, it would be an excellent light on the light if activities within the classroom were organized, such as hygiene, cleanliness day. In this case, the plan of each event is drawn up and organized by the

teacher. This is also one of the effective methods of environmental education of Primary School students by protecting their environment.

Summary of the topic. It is the formation of love for nature in primary school students that is the focus on the future, on progress. It is considered a tribute to nature. Today, the pollution of the atmosphere is caused by toxic fumes emanating from various factories and factories, and the increase in cars in cities is causing this. In the process, it is necessary to teach children not to throw too much toxic fumes and waste into nature. Because, upbringing is taken from youth. And from youth, when they fill their heart, mind with useful information, Our Mother Nature will be grateful to us. On this path, we can use methods and technologies that will give every positive effect. In this regard, in the process of teaching the minds of Primary School students to love the environment, it was environmental education in schools that would have even better results if the organization of events was formed.

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